

Development and optimization of an innovative raft-forming antiemetic gastro-retentive system

Mina Safa Aziz¹

¹ Department of Pharmaceutics, College of Pharmacy, Mustansiriyah University, Baghdad, Iraq

Corresponding author: Mina Safa Aziz (mina_safaa@uomustansiriyah.edu.iq)

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Abstract

Gastro-retentive drug delivery systems are vital for enhancing bioavailability and prolonging gastric residence time, especially for drugs with a short half-life like Ondansetron HCl. This study developed a raft-forming gastroretentive drug delivery system using a polyelectrolyte complex (PEC) of Chitosan and anionic polymers to improve stomach retention, regulate drug release, and enhance therapeutic efficacy. Various formulations were optimized based on polymer type, ratio, cross-linking agent concentration, and hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC K100M). The best formulation (F12: Chitosan: Carbopol 934) showed high entrapment efficiency (98%), drug loading (11.5%), buoyancy (>12 hours), extended drug release (over 12 hours), and a swelling ratio of 1584% at 8 hours. FTIR and DSC confirmed PEC formation and stability, while FE-SEM demonstrated homogeneity. Drug release followed non-Fickian kinetics, indicating that both diffusion and matrix relaxation contributed to the drug release. This PEC-based system shows promise for sustained stomach delivery of Ondansetron HCl, improving therapeutic efficacy and patient adherence.

Keywords

carbopol 934, chitosan, ondansetron hydrochloride, polyelectrolyte complex, xanthan gum

Introduction

The increasing incidence of gastrointestinal illnesses and the constraints of traditional drug delivery techniques present substantial obstacles to successful therapeutic management, despite progress in pharmaceutical sciences.

Oral drug delivery continues to be the predominant and most convenient method for administering drugs owing to its simplicity, patient adherence, and cost efficiency. This is especially beneficial for medications necessitating systemic effects, as it obviates the requirement for invasive treatments. This method poses considerable hurdles, particularly for medications such as Ondansetron Hydrochloride (Ond.

HCl), which experience low bioavailability due to severe first-pass metabolism and a brief biological half-life (Gundu et al. 2020). Traditional oral dosage forms can result in variable plasma drug concentrations, requiring multiple doses and diminishing patient compliance (Tripathi et al. 2019). Gastro-retentive drug delivery devices have emerged as a viable solution to these restrictions. These methods prolong the gastric retention time of the medication, hence improving absorption in the upper gastrointestinal tract, facilitating controlled and prolonged drug release, minimizing plasma concentration variations, and decreasing dose frequency. This approach increases therapeutic effectiveness and augments patient convenience (Dhiman et al. 2023).

A variety of technological approaches have been established for gastro-retentive systems, encompassing muco-adhesive systems, floating systems, magnetic systems, ion exchange resins, expandable systems, unfoldable systems, and raft-forming systems (Karole et al. 2022). Previous studies successfully designed gastro-retentive floating minitables of Ond. HCl for extended emesis management in patients undergoing chemotherapy, using HPMC K15M and Carbopol 971 (Maqbool et al. 2024). The raft formation system entails the generation of a continuous, viscous gel upon interaction with the gastric fluid layer, referred to as the raft. Due to its lower bulk density, the gel-like layer maintains buoyancy above the gastric fluid. Thus, the system preserves its buoyancy in the stomach without affecting the gastric emptying rate for an extended duration. When immersed in gastric contents, the medication is gradually released at the specified rate from the system (Abbas and Hanif 2018; Thapa and Jeong 2018). A recent study developed a raft-forming suspension of famotidine to improve the oral bioavailability of narrow absorption window drugs by enhancing gastric residence time (GRT) and preventing gastro-oesophageal reflux disease (GERD). The formulation aimed to prolong drug release and provide effective anti-reflux action, demonstrating the potential for improved therapeutic outcomes (Munusamy and Shanmugasundharam 2024). Another recent study aimed to formulate a novel raft-forming system incorporating curcumin-Eudragit® EPO solid dispersions that were developed to prolong gastric residence time and provide controlled release of curcumin for treating gastric ulcers. Solid dispersions were prepared using a solvent evaporation method at a 1:5 curcumin-to-Eudragit® EPO ratio to enhance solubility and dissolution. The raft-forming formulations, composed of Sodium alginate and calcium carbonate, formed a gelled raft within 1 minute and sustained buoyancy in acidic conditions, releasing 60–85% of curcumin over 8 hours; the findings highlight the potential of raft-forming systems for stomach-specific delivery of poorly soluble lipophilic drugs like curcumin (Kerdsakundee et al. 2015).

Polyelectrolyte complex (PEC) systems have emerged as a viable and new method in polymeric drug delivery, providing improved efficacy and adaptability (Moustafine et al. 2005). Chitosan (CS), a cationic polysaccharide obtained from the deacetylation of chitin in marine crustaceans, has garnered considerable interest among polymeric carriers due to its biocompatibility, safety, and distinctive functional characteristics (Anitha et al. 2009). In acidic settings, chitosan's amine groups readily undergo protonation, facilitating solubility and interaction with anionic polymers, while it remains insoluble in neutral or aqueous environments without change (Zhang et al. 2010). These attributes render chitosan an exemplary choice for forming PEC systems with anionic polymers, facilitating extended stomach retention and delayed release of drugs (Shao et al. 2015). In a recent investigation aimed at synthesizing and characterizing CS – Sod. alginate PEC for use as an active excipient in formulating

fast-dispersible phenytoin sodium tablets. The PEC was formed via ionic cross-linking of the polymers and evaluated for micromeritic properties and flow behavior, which were found suitable for tablet formulation; the findings suggest that the chitosan–alginate PEC is a promising excipient for developing fast-dispersible tablets with enhanced drug delivery properties (Malviya and Srivastava 2011). Another recent study designed a CS and neem gum polysaccharide (NGP) polyelectrolyte complex-based allantoin-loaded (CS/NGP-AT) biocomposite film for improved wound healing. The optimized formulation showed controlled water absorption, uptake capacity, and enhanced mechanical properties. Wound healing experiments showed a higher rate of recovery within 14 days.

This research investigates the creation of an innovative raft-forming gastro-retentive drug delivery system for Ond. HCl, utilizing the characteristics of PEC. The formulation is engineered to float and create a raft over gastrointestinal fluids, assuring prolonged gastric retention and controlled medication release. This method overcomes the shortcomings of traditional oral dose forms, including inadequate bioavailability and the necessity for frequent administration, hence improving patient adherence and therapeutic results. To our knowledge, the creation of raft-forming capsules employing two oppositely charged hydrophilic polymers has not been previously recorded, underscoring the originality of our research. Chitosan was mixed with three distinct anionic polymers (Sodium alginate, Carbopol 934, and Xanthan gum). Non-ionic polymer HPMC K100M was also investigated. Thorough assessments, encompassing *in vitro* drug release and buoyancy evaluations at gastric pH, were performed to evaluate the system's efficacy. At the same time, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) were employed to examine potential interactions between formulation constituents and the thermal stability of the drug and polymers. Scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) elucidated the morphological characteristics of the formulations, affirming structural integrity and homogeneity. This comprehensive assessment demonstrates the potential of the proposed PEC-based raft system as an effective and sustained method for gastric delivery of Ond. HCl.

Experimental

Materials and methods

Ondansetron hydrochloride dihydrate (Ond. HCl) powder was acquired from Qufu Hongly Chemical Industry Co., Ltd. (China). High M.wt. Chitosan Powder (1000–2000 cps) was acquired from Glentham Life Science Ltd. (United Kingdom, UK). Carbopol 934 (Carb. 934) powder was supplied by Beijing Jin Ming Biotechnology Co., Ltd. (China). Xanthan gum powder and Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC K100M) were provided by Beijing ZhongShuo Pharmaceutical Technology Development

Co., Ltd. (China). Sodium Alginate (Sod. alginate) powder was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. Calcium Chloride (CaCl_2) was acquired from Central Drug House (P) Ltd. (Gujarat, India). Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) was acquired from ACS Chemicals (Gujarat, India). Glacial acetic acid solution was acquired from ACS Chemicals (Gujarat, India). Hydrochloric acid solution was supplied by Thomas Baker (Chemicals) Pvt. Ltd.

Preparation of raft-forming PEC

Different formulations of raft-forming PEC of Ond. HCl were prepared using oppositely charged polymers, as shown in Table 1. (Mujtaba et al. 2024). Initially, Chitosan was dissolved in 2% acetic acid under continuous stirring to form a homogenous gel. Pre-weighed drug powder (20 mg) was then incorporated into Chitosan gel with thorough mixing for 30 minutes to achieve a uniform Chitosan-drug homogenization. An additional step formulation containing calcium chloride (CaCl_2) as a cross-linker (F6, F7, F8, and F11) with varying concentrations of cross-linker 1%, 2%, and 4% was prepared and added to the Chitosan-drug mixture with stirring. Subsequently, an anionic polymer, dissolved in deionized water, was incrementally incorporated into the Chitosan-drug mixture under continuous stirring, with the pH regulated to (5–5.5), utilizing 4% NaOH to enhance electrostatic interactions. The resulting complex was applied to a petri dish and allowed to dry at 40 °C for a short period of 6 hr to accelerate the drying process. After this initial drying phase, the sample was removed from the oven and allowed to dry completely at room temperature in the laboratory environment for approximately 3–4 days. Fig. 1 illustrates the PEC before and after drying. Then, it was stored in a desiccator for future testing purposes. The dried PEC equivalent to 20 mg of Ond. HCl was manually encapsulated in hard gelatin capsules (size 00) for further studies. To ensure accurate dosing, the filled capsules were tested for weight variation and content uniformity. The results confirmed that the capsules were within the acceptable limits of USP pharmacopeial standards (results not mentioned).

Evaluation of the raft-forming system

Assessment of entrapment efficiency and percent drug loading

A specific amount of dried complex, corresponding to 20 mg of the drug, was broken down into small flakes using a mortar and pestle and accurately measured. It was then placed in a beaker containing 100 mL of 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2) and permitted to stand for 2 hours in order to swell and burst, with periodic agitation, using a high-speed magnetic stirrer set at 300 rpm and a temperature of 37 ± 0.5 °C. The mixture was centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 10 minutes, then the supernatant fraction was further filtered using a 0.45 μm syringe filter, and 1 mL of the filtrate was diluted with 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2) to achieve a final volume of 50 mL.

The absorbance of the solution was quantified at 310 nm, and the concentration of the drug was obtained via the equation of the Ond. HCl calibration curve (Görög 2018). Entrapment efficiency and drug loading percentages were calculated according to the following formula (Ahuja and Bhatt 2018; Verma et al. 2021; Lateef et al. 2024):

$$\text{Entrapment efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Total drug added} - \text{Untrapped drug}}{\text{Total drug added}} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

$$\% \text{ Drug loading} = \frac{\text{Amount of Ond.HCL in PEC particulate}}{\text{Weight of PEC particulate}} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Determination % yield

The practical weight of the complex was determined after drying using an electrical balance (Kern ALS 220-4N, Germany), and then the % yield of the complex was determined using this equation (Lateef et al. 2024):

$$\% \text{ yield} = \frac{\text{practical weight of complex}}{\text{theoretical weight of complex}} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

Assessment of in vitro buoyancy

The floating lag time (FLT) and total floating time (TFT) were employed to assess the buoyancy characteristics of the floated complex. A quantity of dried complex containing an equivalent of 20 mg of drug was accurately weighed, loaded into a gelatin capsule, transferred into a 100 mL beaker containing 100 mL of 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2) solution, and stirred using a magnetic stirrer at a temperature of 37 ± 0.5 °C and a rate of 50 rpm. The duration necessary for the dissolution of the capsule's gelatin shell and the complex to float to the top of the medium and form a raft called FLT was recognized and calculated. Then, the beaker was removed from the stirrer and left for 24 hrs. to determine the duration of floating (TFT) (Kamsali et al. 2020).

Measurement of raft strength

The raft's strength was evaluated utilizing a double-pan balance. The PEC raft formulations were submerged in a graduated beaker containing 150 mL of 0.1 N HCl solution held at 37 °C on the left side. The beaker was equilibrated by incorporating an additional beaker containing 150 mL of water on the right side. A metal wire probe in the shape of an L was placed into the beaker on the left side and maintained just beneath the surface of the HCl solution during the whole raft development process. The strength was quantified in grams based on the weight of the displaced water (Najm and Ali 2019).

Raft weight and volume

A graduated beaker containing 150 mL of 0.1 N HCl was used. Before raft formation, the beaker's weight (W_1) and volume (V_1) were measured. Then, the formulation was positioned in the beaker and allowed to settle for several minutes, allowing it to form a raft; the weight of the beaker after raft formation (W_2) and the position attained by each

Figure 1. PEC before and after drying.

Table 1. Component of the PEC floating formulations holding 20 mg of Ond HCl.

Formula code	Formula components					
	Chitosan (mg)	Sod. Alginate (mg)	HPMC K100M (mg)	Xanthan gum (mg)	Carb. 934 (mg)	CaCl ₂
F1	120 (20 mg/mL)	60 (10 mg/mL)	-	-	-	-
F2	40 (7 mg/mL)	-	-	-	-	-
F3	60 (10 mg/mL)	60 (10 mg/mL)	-	-	-	-
F4	60 (10 mg/mL)	120 (20 mg/mL)	-	-	-	-
F5	60 (10 mg/mL)	180 (30 mg/mL)	-	-	-	-
F6	120 (20 mg/mL)	60 (10 mg/mL)	-	-	-	1%
F7	120 (20 mg/mL)	60 (10 mg/mL)	-	-	-	2%
F8	120 (20 mg/mL)	60 (10 mg/mL)	-	-	-	4%
F9	120 (20 mg/mL)	-	60 (10 mg/mL)	-	-	-
F10	120 (20 mg/mL)	-	-	60 (10 mg/mL)	-	-
F11	120 (20 mg/mL)	-	-	60 (10 mg/mL)	-	2%
F12	120 (20 mg/mL)	-	-	-	60 (10 mg/mL)	-

*Volume used to dissolve chitosan: 6 mL of 2% acetic acid.

**Volume used to dissolve anionic and non-ionic polymer: 6 mL.

***6 mL of 1%, 2%, and 4% CaCl₂ aqueous solutions containing 60 mg, 120 mg, and 240 mg CaCl₂ respectively, were added as cross-linkers.

****All the above amounts are for a single dose.

*****The drug concentration dissolved in the chitosan gel solution was 3.33 mg/mL, and the final drug concentration in the prepared complex was 1.7 mg/mL.

raft at the top were noted externally on the beaker (V2) and recorded. Subsequently, the weight of the raft was measured using the following equation (Najm and Ali 2019):

$$\text{Raft weight} = W2 - W1 \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

The raft volume was determined using the equation (Najm and Ali 2019):

$$\text{Raft volume} = V2 - V1 \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

In vitro dissolution studies

The dissolution of Ond. HCl capsules was analyzed in a solution of 900 mL 0.1 N HCl with a pH of 1.2 using the dissolution device USP Type II (paddle type, Copley dissolution 8000, Copley Scientific, UK) set at 50 rpm and a temperature of 37 °C. Capsules were inserted into each device jar for 12 hrs at predetermined intervals (every quarter of an hour during the first hour, then every hour until 12 hours); 5 mL from each sample was extracted and substituted with an equivalent amount of fresh dissolution

medium. Subsequently, the samples were filtered using 0.45 µm syringe filters and analyzed using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1650 pc-Japan) at a wavelength of 310 nm. The trials were performed in triplicate (n = 3) at each time interval, and the mean value was reported (Safa Mohammed et al. 2023).

Variables affecting the release of Ond. HCl

Effect of (Chitosan - Sod. alginate) ratio

Four formulations (F1, F3, F4, and F5) were intended to assess the impact of changing the polymer ratio of (Chitosan: Sod. alginate) (2:1), (1:1), (1:2), and (1:3), respectively, on drug release from the complex.

Effect of anionic polymer type

Three types of anionic polymers (Sod. alginate, Xanthan gum, and Carb. 934) were used in the preparation of different formulations (F1, F10, and F12), respectively, in a ratio of 2:1, and their effect on retard drug release was studied.

Effect of cross-linking agent percentage

Varied proportions of the cross-linking agent CaCl_2 (1%, 2%, and 4%) were used in the formulations (F6, F7, and F8), respectively, and their effect on enhancing ionic interactions between Chitosan and Sod. alginate to form a robust drug-entrapment complex was studied.

Effect of cross-linking agent

In this variable, two formulations were chosen, one with a cross-linker and the other without a cross-linker, to study the effect of using a cross-linker on the Ond. HCl release. (F10 and F11) containing Xanthan gum and (F1 and F8) containing Sod. alginate were used in this study.

Effect of non-ionic polymer on Chitosan - Ond. HCl complex

The non-ionic polymer HPMC K100M was incorporated into the F9 formulation, and its impact on delaying drug release was analyzed and compared to the F2 formulation, which consisted solely of Chitosan and Ond. HCl.

Swelling study

The swelling characteristics of formulations (F8, F9, F11, and F12) were assessed in simulated gastric juice at 0.1 N HCl pH 1.2. The pre-weighed formulations (W0) were immersed in 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2). At designated intervals (15, 30, and 45 minutes; 1 hour; and then hourly up to 12 hours), the swollen formulations were withdrawn and weighed promptly after being wiped with filter paper to exclude any surface moisture (W1). The experiment was conducted in triplets, and the swelling index results were reported as the averages. The swelling index for each sample measured at a time (t) was computed using the following algorithm (Younis et al. 2018):

$$\text{Swelling index} = \frac{W1-W0}{W0} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

Modeling of kinetic drug release

The Ond. HCl cumulative amount released from the formulated complex-forming raft capsules at various time intervals was analyzed using zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas to clarify the medication release mechanism (Paarakh et al. 2019).

Determination of optimized formulation

The chosen PEC raft formulation was assigned for further analysis: FTIR, DSC, and FE-SEM.

Morphological examination

Examines the morphological surface using a field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM). The samples were permitted to air dry prior to being affixed to

glass stubs with pre-applied double-sided adhesive. The stub was subsequently positioned in a fine-coat ion sputter for gold deposition. The surface morphology of optimized formula F12 was analyzed at a 30 kV accelerating voltage utilizing an Inspect F50 SEM (Netherlands) (Chen et al. 2018).

Differential scanning calorimetry

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) is utilized to analyze Ond. HCl, Chitosan, Carbopol 934, and drug-loaded PEC formulation. A sample of approximately 10 mg is placed in aluminum pans and analyzed throughout a temperature range of 25 °C to 400 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C/min. An inert atmosphere is created by continually replacing air with nitrogen gas at a rate of 50 mL/min (Mohamed et al. 2022).

Fourier transforms infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

A small amount of Ond. HCl powder, Chitosan, Carbopol 934, and PEC formulation-loaded drug sample, approximately 5 mg, was ground, combined with KBr, and compressed to create a KBr disc. The disc was examined throughout a 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} spectral range (Muhsin et al. 2022).

Analytical statistics

The results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the level of statistical significance, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

Results and discussion

Assessment of the raft formation system

Assessment of % entrapment efficiency, % drug loading, % yield, and in vitro buoyancy

According to the results in Table 2, all the prepared PEC raft capsules showed a high entrapment efficiency and % drug loading in the range of (90% - 98%) and (10.5% - 12%) respectively, for all formulations except for F2, which shows low entrapment efficiency and % drug loading (78.3%, 7%) respectively. The yield percentage for all formulations (F1 - F12) was high (80% - 90%), as seen in Table 2. The high entrapment efficiency and % drug loading in all prepared PEC raft capsules demonstrate the efficacy of the two polymers in forming a stable polyelectrolyte complex, suggesting that the technique used in the formulation preparation is reliable and effective (Anitha et al. 2009). The low entrapment efficiency observed in F2 (Chitosan: Ond. HCl) is attributed to the weak

Table 2. Demonstrate entrapment efficiency, % drug loading, % yield, and buoyancy characteristics of the drug in different capsule formulas (n = 3, mean \pm SD).

Formula number	% Entrapment efficiency	% Drug loading	% yield	TFT (hr)
F1	95 \pm 2.517	10.5 \pm 0.503	85.4 \pm 1.75	> 12
F2	78.3 \pm 1.662	7 \pm 0.251	80 \pm 2.762	1
F3	92 \pm 1.950	11.5 \pm 0.251	86 \pm 1.401	8
F4	95.7 \pm 2.851	12 \pm 0.351	81 \pm 2.517	> 12
F5	92.2 \pm 1.290	11.5 \pm 0.361	83 \pm 1.258	> 12
F6	95.7 \pm 1.401	12 \pm 0.252	81 \pm 1.0786	>12
F7	94.8 \pm 1.914	11.9 \pm 0.503	84.4 \pm 1.833	>12
F8	92.3 \pm 1.692	11.6 \pm 0.306	88.7 \pm 1.662	>12
F9	89.9 \pm 2.026	11.3 \pm 0.404	82 \pm 2.610	>12
F10	94 \pm 2	11.8 \pm 0.404	81 \pm 1.617	>12
F11	95.4 \pm 2.450	12 \pm 0.404	82.5 \pm 1.818	>12
F12	98 \pm 1.258	11.5 \pm 0.5	90 \pm 1.756	>12

electrostatic interactions between Chitosan and Ond. HCl. Unlike anionic polymers, which form strong complementary charges with Chitosan, Ond. HCl lacks sufficient ionic interactions to form a stable PEC. As a result, a significant portion of the drug remained untrapped, leading to lower entrapment efficiency (Jana et al. 2014).

Regarding the buoyancy study, the FLT for all formulations (F1 - F12) was instantaneously right away from the time the capsule opened, which was 5 minutes. The TFT shows non-significant differences between formulations except for F2, which sank after 1 hr, as presented in Table 2. As the cationic Chitosan polymer reacts with the anionic polymer through electrostatic interaction, a viscous gel formed upon contact with gastric fluid will be hydrated, swell, and entrap air between the formed pores, forming a low-density structure that floats for a long period of time. Chitosan alone cannot create the same floating behavior because it cannot construct a comparably buoyant structure (Verma et al. 2012). Fig. 2 illustrates the *in vitro* buoyancy of raft-forming PEC.

Raft weight, volume, and strength

The raft strength ranged from 5.5 \pm 0.18 to 7.9 \pm 0.12 g, as assessed by the modified balance method. The weight and volume of the raft varied from 0.102 \pm 0.15 to 0.304 \pm 0.12 g and from 4 \pm 0.29 to 5 \pm 0.33 mL, respectively, as depicted in Fig. 3. The results highlight the impact of polymer ratio and cross-linking agent on the raft-forming

properties of PEC. Formula F2 lacking Sod. alginate exhibits lower strength, weight, and volume compared to other formulations, emphasizing the importance of the presence of Sod. alginate and its role in forming a stable, rigid complex with desired raft properties (Hastuti and Hadi 2023; Wang and Roman 2023).

Variables affecting polyelectrolyte complex raft formulation

Effect of changing polymer ratio of complex

Four formulations (F1, F3, F4, and F5) were employed to examine the impact of alteration of the polymer's ratio of (Chitosan: Sod. alginate) on the rate of the drug release, as depicted in Fig. 4. A significant ($p < 0.05$) delay in the drug rate release was seen as the quantity of Chitosan increased. The ratio of Chitosan: Sod. alginate markedly affects the medication release profile. Chitosan, a cationic polymer, engages with the anionic Sod. alginate to create a compact polymeric network via ionic interactions. Formulation F1 (2:1) shows the slowest release profile, with 42% of Ond. HCl released during the initial 2 hours and 81% after 8 hours. In contrast, formulations F3 (1:1), F4 (1:2), and F5 (1:3) exhibited burst releases of 60–70% initially and 84–92% after 8 hours. The reduced release rate in F1 is ascribed to elevated Chitosan concentration, which generates a viscous gel layer and extends the diffusional

Figure 2. The *in vitro* floating behavior of polyelectrolyte complex raft formulation.

Figure 3. The assessment criteria for the PEC raft-forming formulations.

Figure 4. The effect of (Chitosan: Sod. alginate) ratios on Ond. HCl release from PEC raft formulations.

pathway, resulting in a dense matrix that obstructs drug diffusion. While formulations with increasing Sod. alginate concentration (F1, F4, and F5) exhibited quick water absorption owing to the hydrophilic properties of Sod. alginate, resulting in swelling, enhanced matrix porosity, and expedited drug release (Li et al. 2015). This result agrees with a previous study that aimed to study the possibility of utilizing (Chitosan - Sod. alginate) tablets for the delayed release of highly water-soluble medications through adjusting formulation parameters. It was shown that augmenting the ratio of (Chitosan - Sod. alginate) led to a delay in drug delivery (KHAN et al. 2020).

Effect of anionic polymer type

Three formulations were prepared using different types of anionic polymer F1 (Chitosan: Sod. alginate), F10 (Chitosan: Xanthan gum), and F12 (Chitosan: Carb. 934) with a ratio of (2:1) illustrated in Fig. 5. A considerable ($p < 0.05$) slowdown in the release rate of Ond. HCl from F12 in comparison to F1 and F10. The type of polymer utilized in PEC formulations markedly affects drug release. The Chitosan: Carb. 934 complex demonstrated improved stability and prolonged release, with merely 24% of the medication released within the initial 2 hours and 84% after 12 hours. The dense gel layer generated by ionic

Figure 5. The impact of several anionic polymers that interact with Chitosan on the release of Ond. HCl from the PEC raft formulation at a 2:1 ratio.

interactions between the carboxyl groups of Carbopol and the amine groups of Chitosan hinders drug diffusion (Panzade and Puranik 2010). In contrast, the Chitosan: Sod. alginate complex exhibited a modest burst release (45% in 2 hours) attributable to its hydrophilic characteristics, leading to enhanced matrix porosity and accelerated drug diffusion. The Chitosan: Xanthan gum combination exhibited instability, resulting in a rapid release of 75% within 2 hours and inadequate drug entrapment attributed to diminished ionic interactions (Lopes et al. 2018). This observation agreed with the previous investigations aimed at developing and evaluating various bio-erodible spongy composites containing rosuvastatin to ascertain their efficacy in promoting bone repair and rejuvenation (Ibrahim and Fahmy 2016).

Effect of cross-linking agent percentage

The impact of CaCl_2 concentration as an ion crosslinking agent on Ond. HCl release is displayed in Fig. 6. The findings demonstrate that elevating the concentration of CaCl_2 from 1% (F6), 2% (F7), to 4% (F8) significantly influenced ($p < 0.05$) the reduction of the release rate. It was noted that increasing the crosslinker concentration improved *in vitro* drug release; at first 2 hr, F6 displayed burst release

Figure 6. The effect of increasing cross-linker CaCl_2 percentage on Ond. HCl release.

of 71% compared to F7 and F8, which displayed (43% and 27%) release, respectively. This is attributed to inadequate cross-linking, leading to diminished drug entrapment; then, at 8 hr, F8 showed (81%) while F6 and F7 (95% and 84%) drug release, respectively. Ond. HCl release continuously raised slowly for F7 and F8, while for F6, it ended at 9 hr. This effect is ascribed to the rise in the number of Ca^{++} ions, which enhance the crosslinking with the polymer chains to create a two-dimensional framework structure incorporating Sod. alginate within the alginate matrices results in an elevated density of the polymer matrix and, subsequently, a further increase of the diffusional pathway (Amiruddin et al. 2023). A previous study aimed to create and analyze pH-sensitive, swellable mucoadhesive microbeads for prolonged atorvastatin release using polymers with hydrophilic characteristics and varying analyzing parameters. It was observed that beads with a higher amount of cross-linking demonstrated superior durability compared to those with fewer cross-linkages. Moreover, the atorvastatin release rate in acidic conditions was notably slower and more extended (Reddy and Nagabhusanam 2017).

Effect of cross-linking agent

The release profiles and the effect of CaCl_2 as an ionic cross-linking agent on the release of Ond. HCl. are illustrated in Fig. 7a. Formulation F8 (Chitosan: Sod. alginate) with 4% CaCl_2 exhibited a significantly slower release ($p < 0.05$) compared to F1 (Chitosan: Sod. alginate) without a cross-linker. This retardation in drug release can be ascribed to the presence of Ca^{2+} ions, which enhance

cross-linking within the polymer matrix. The resulting two-dimensional network structure is formed through interactions between calcium ions and Sod. alginate increases the density of the polymer matrix and extends the diffusional pathway for drug release. These findings align with previous studies investigating the role of calcium ions in modulating lysozyme release from Chitosan-Sod. alginate complexes, demonstrating that CaCl_2 incorporation reduces the release rate (Wu et al. 2018). Similarly, research on cross-linked polyelectrolyte films for buccal drug delivery reported that cross-linking improved structural stability and drug-loading capacity while prolonging release, in contrast to the rapid release observed with non-cross-linked formulations (Pilicheva et al. 2020).

The effect of incorporating the cross-linking agent CaCl_2 into the Chitosan-Xanthan gum complex on the release of Ond. HCl is illustrated in Fig. 7b; formulation F11, formulated with CaCl_2 , had a release rate that was significantly slower ($p < 0.05$) compared to F10 (without CaCl_2). Specifically, at 2 hours and 8 hours, the release rates for F11 were 42.5% and 91%, respectively, while F10 exhibited faster release rates of 75.3% and 94%. This delayed release in F11 is attributed to the cross-linking effect of CaCl_2 , which enhances structural integrity by forming a more tightly bound polymer network. This increases the matrix strength and diffusion pathway, enabling sustained drug release. These findings align with prior research on tacrolimus microbeads, where increased CaCl_2 concentrations were shown to delay drug release by improving the polymer matrix's stability and entrapment efficiency (Bhupathyraaj and Pole 2020).

Effect of addition of non-ionic polymer on Chitosan - Ond. HCl complex

The incorporation of the nonionic polymer HPMC K100M into Chitosan: Ond. HCl (F9) led to a considerable ($p < 0.05$) delay in the release of the drug, as illustrated in Fig. 8. The non-ionic polymer HPMC K100M is a cellulose derivative and exhibits a higher molecular weight, rendering it more viscous, 75,000 to 140,000 cps. (Guarve and Kriplani 2021) Chitosan has a positive amine group ($-\text{NH}_3^+$) capable of forming a hydrogen bond with the Ond. HCl hydroxyl and carbonyl functional group, but this ionic interaction of Chitosan-Ond. HCl is not strong

Figure 7. a. The release profiles and the impact of CaCl_2 as an ion crosslinking agent on Ond. HCl release; **b.** The effect of adding cross-linker CaCl_2 to chitosan - xanthan gum on Ond. HCl release.

Figure 8. The effect of the addition of a non-ionic polymer to the Chitosan - Ond. HCl complex on the release profile.

enough to create a dense, compact network that retards drug release. Even though non-ionic HPMC K100M was added, the sustained release effect may be due to HPMC's high viscous gel barrier; it absorbs water, forms a gelatinous layer that expands, and initially releases the medication in a regulated fashion, forming a viscous gel to manage drug release further (Guarve and Kriplani 2021). This corresponds with a previous study examining the possible application of anionic κ -carrageenan and nonionic Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMCK4) to enhance the structural integrity of directly compressed Chitosan tablets containing Naproxen Sodium (Bhise et al. 2007).

Swelling study

Four formulations, F8, F9, F11, and F12, were chosen for further assessment due to their exceptional performance in critical criteria, such as elevated entrapment efficiency, yield %, adequate drug loading, advantageous raft characterization, and good *in vitro* drug release profiles. The chosen formulations underwent swelling and kinetic studies to evaluate their hydration capacity and matrix integrity, which are essential parameters affecting drug release kinetics and buoyancy in gastrointestinal settings. As seen in Fig. 9, the maximum swelling ratios of formulations F8, F9, F11, and F12 were 1193%, 1725%, 1624%, and 1584% at 1 hr, 1 hr, 2 hr, and 8 hr, respectively, then followed by a decline in the polymer swelling weight. F12 exhibited a substantial swelling index ($P < 0.05$) compared to F8, F9,

Figure 9. The swelling behavior of formulations F8, F9, F11, and F12.

and F11. Polyelectrolyte complexes exhibit pH-responsive swelling. Fluctuations in pH modify the charge equilibrium of the ionic polymer and Chitosan, consequently influencing their contact degree and resulting in swelling owing to complex dissociation (Colinet et al. 2010). In their anhydrous condition, PEC polymeric matrices exist in coiled configurations that transition to expanded conformations upon water absorption as the amine group of Chitosan pKa (6.20) will be protonated in acidic media pH 1.2 while a hydrophilic anionic polymer having a carboxylate group will not be ionized in acidic media. As the abundance of negative charges from the ionized groups increased, the electrostatic repulsion forces among the anions inside the Chitosan chains intensified. The repulsion and diminished electrostatic interactions destabilized the network and facilitated the mobility of the Chitosan chains. As the polymer chain elongates, hydrogen bonds with water are established, leading to significant polymer swelling. The ionized polymer will enhance osmotic forces owing to the ion concentration gradient within and outside the polymeric matrix, leading to increased water absorption or swelling. The ionization of polymers causes similar charges on neighboring polymer units to repel one another, hence enhancing water absorption (Fajardo et al. 2010; Deshkar et al. 2023). A previous study investigated mechanisms of drug release from Chitosan-anionic polymer matrix tablets utilizing six distinct anionic polymers and two model pharmaceuticals. The six polymers were classified into three categories according to their characteristics: those readily soluble in solute infiltration (Eudragite), hydrophilic matrices exhibiting rapid erosion (Sod. alginate, Carrageenan, and Carboxy methyl cellulose), and hydrophilic matrices demonstrating slow erosion (Carbomer and Xanthan gum). The study demonstrated that the properties of the anionic polymers produced varying degrees of swelling in the control sample after 24 hours (Li et al. 2014).

Examination of the mathematical framework for kinetic drug release

The dissolution data of different formulations were evaluated using various kinetic models to assess their *in vitro* release patterns, as detailed in Table 3. The drug release kinetics results indicated that the R^2 value for formulation F8 (Chitosan: Sod. alginate: 4% CaCl_2) was high when assessed under zero-order kinetics, signifying that the rate of drug release from this formulation is independent of the drug concentration. F9 (Chitosan: HPMC), F11 (Chitosan: Xanthan gum: 2% CaCl_2), and F12 (Chitosan: Carbopol 934) exhibited the highest R^2 values when evaluated under first-order release kinetics, signifying that the release is concentration-dependent. The mechanism of drug release was ascertained using the Korsmeyer-Peppas model on the data, yielding n values between 0.692 and 0.884. This indicates that all formulations exhibited anomalous non-Fickian transport, suggesting drug diffusion from the hydrated matrix and polymer relaxation affect drug release (Verma et al. 2013; Lv et al. 2018).

Table 3. Kinetics drug release for prepared raft-forming PEC formulations.

Formula code	Zero-order		First order		Higuchi		Korsmeyer Peppas		
	K_0 (min ⁻¹)	R ²	K_1 (min ⁻¹)	R ²	K_H (mg. min ^{-1/2})	R ²	K_{kp} (mg. min ⁻ⁿ)	R ²	n
F8	0.240	0.9887	0.003	0.9853	3.342	0.8885	0.449	0.9944	0.884
F9	0.247	0.9620	0.004	0.9966	3.512	0.9419	0.994	0.9993	0.743
F11	0.363	0.9220	0.005	0.9835	3.979	0.9520	1.636	0.9948	0.692
F12	0.176	0.9844	0.003	0.9972	2.935	0.9178	0.482	0.9979	0.824

Choosing the optimal formula

Formula F12 was identified as the optimal PEC raft-forming formulation based on the results, which include high entrapment efficiency, % drug loading, % yield, and good floating ability of (98 %, 11.5%, 90%, > 12 hrs.), respectively. It also has good raft properties (weight, volume, and strength). Furthermore, it exhibited a sustained *in vitro* release profile for 12 hrs. without burst release. This optimum formula was further characterized to confirm complex formation.

Scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM)

Morphological analysis of the optimum formula (F12) (Chitosan: Carb. 934 loaded with Ond. HCl), depicted in Fig. 10, revealed an uneven surface morphology that aligns with polyelectrolyte complexation, wherein electrostatic interactions may induce such aggregation. The lack of smooth, crystalline formations indicates successful complexation and encapsulation of Ond. HCl within the Chitosan - Carbopol matrix (Deka et al. 2016).

Differential scanning calorimetric

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) is a beneficial technique for identifying interactions between complex components. Such interactions are reflected through various parameters, including the absence of endothermic peaks, the emergence of new peaks, alterations in peak shapes, changes in onset and peak temperatures, modifications to the melting point, and variations in relative peak area or enthalpy. The DSC thermogram of the

separate components and their combinations is presented in Fig. 11. The pure Ond. HCl shows an endothermic peak at 185 °C, confirming its crystalline structure. A large endotherm at 85 °C indicates dehydration, as it is a dihydrate. These results also align with the previous literature (Mizoguchi and Uekusa 2018).

Pure Chitosan DSC thermogram displayed an endothermic peak at 85 °C, indicating water evaporation, and a significant exothermic peak at around 280 °C, indicative of the gradual decomposition of Chitosan (El-Gawad 2012). The DSC thermogram of pure Carbopol 934 exhibited two endothermic peaks at 75 °C and 238 °C, signifying the presence of bound water or moisture since it is a hydrophilic polymer, and an exothermic peak at around 300 °C, suggesting the onset of Carbopol decomposition (Yusif et al. 2016).

The thermogram of the physical combination exhibited a superimposition of peaks corresponding to the two polymers, while the thermogram of Chitosan - Carbopol - Ond. HCl exhibited an endothermic distinctive peak of the drug, suggesting no drug-polymer interaction (El-Gawad et al. 2012). Dried PEC of Chitosan - Carbopol 934 loaded Ond. HCl showed an endothermic peak near 100 °C, which may be linked to the vaporization of water from the hydrophilic polymer group and the dihydrate moiety of the drug. Carbopol's endothermic peak around 238 °C as well as Ond. HCl's characteristic sharp endothermic peak has disappeared, suggesting that most ondansetron is integrated within the polymeric matrix and uniformly distributed at the molecular level generated by the complexation of Chitosan and Carbopol. The peaks associated with Chitosan and Carbopol vanished, and a linked peak emerged at around 300 °C, suggesting the complex

Figure 10. The FE-SEM of PEC of Chitosan: Carb. 934 loaded with Ond. HCl.

Figure 11. Illustrates the DSC of the PEC of pure drug, Chitosan, Carbopol 934, physical mixture (Chitosan-Carbopol), physical mixture (Chitosan: Carbopol) with Ond. HCl, and optimum formula F12.

formation (Darwesh et al. 2018). The characteristic peaks obtained for Ond. HCl and polymers confirm their purity. The appearance of a new peak of Chitosan and Carb. 934 and the disappearance of the broad peak of pure drug suggest complex formation, and the drug is dispersed and stabilized in the complex (Darwesh et al. 2018).

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

The spectrum obtained from FTIR is a proficient method for verifying the purity of drugs and polymers, examining drug-polymer and polymer-polymer interactions, and validating complex formation illustrated in Fig. 12. Pure Ond. HCl exhibited distinctive bands at 3483.44 cm^{-1} (O-H stretching), 3408.29 cm^{-1} (N-H stretching), 1635.64 cm^{-1} (C = O stretching in the aromatic ketone group), 1531.48 cm^{-1} (C = C aromatic stretching), 1280.73 cm^{-1} (C-N stretching), and 756.10 cm^{-1} (C-H bending), consistent with its structural features (Nguyen et al. 2020). Chitosan showed bands at 3466 cm^{-1} and 3302 cm^{-1} (O-H and N-H stretching), 1654 cm^{-1} (C = O amide I band), 1593 cm^{-1} (N-H bending, amide II band), and 1153 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching) (Elhaes et al. 2024). Similarly, Carbopol 934 exhibited peaks at 3378 cm^{-1} (O-H stretching), 1705 cm^{-1} (C = O stretching of the carboxyl group), and 1244 cm^{-1} (O-H bending) (Poozhikanadake et al. 2013; Mahmood et al. 2023). The physical mixture

Figure 12. Illustrates the FTIR of the PEC of pure drug, Chitosan, Carbopol 934, physical mixture (Chitosan: Carbopol), physical mixture (Chitosan: Carbopol) with Ond. HCl, PEC (Chitosan: Carbopol), and optimum formula F12.

with Ond. HCl retained the drug's characteristic peaks, though with reduced intensity, likely due to dilution effects (Darwesh et al. 2018). When polymers are mixed together, interactions among molecules may occur, leading to changes in the IR spectra of the mixture, such as band shifting, broadening, and the appearance of newer absorption bands, signifying polymers' miscibility (Stuart 2004). For optimum formula F12, a broad peak around 3400 cm^{-1} indicated hydrogen bonding between Chitosan, Carbopol, and the dihydrate form of Ond. HCl. Newer bands at 1556.43 cm^{-1} and 1454 cm^{-1} were attributed to overlapping peaks from asymmetric COO₂ stretching (Carbopol) and NH₃⁺ bending (Chitosan). A peak at 1410 cm^{-1} further confirmed symmetric COO₂ stretching, highlighting electrostatic interactions between Chitosan and Carbopol. The slight shifts and reduced intensity of Ond. HCl peaks confirmed its encapsulation and stabilization within the PEC matrix, the formation of a new peak between Chitosan and Carbopol, and the shifting of the carboxyl group of Carbopol, demonstrating successful complex formation (Kao et al. 2006; Silva et al. 2008; Suhail et al. 2023).

Conclusion

This research effectively created an innovative raft-forming PEC approach for the gastro-retentive administration of Ond. HCl. The approach integrated Chitosan with multiple anionic polymers to augment stomach retention, prolong drug release, and boost bioavailability. Formula F12 was identified as the superior formulation, exhibiting 98% entrapment efficiency, buoyancy beyond 12 hours, and prolonged drug release over the same duration. The exceptional performance of F12 was ascribed to the robust interaction between Chitosan and Carbopol 934, resulting in a stable PEC matrix with significant raft strength and efficient drug encapsulation. The characterization using DSC, FTIR, and SEM validated the effective encapsulation of Ond. HCl and the robust electrostatic interactions within the PEC matrix. This study underscores the promise of raft-forming PEC systems as novel approaches

for gastroretentive medication delivery. The modified F12 formulation represents a significant advancement in this area, with its enhanced in vitro performance suggesting potential for further development. Future studies should focus on in vivo evaluation to assess its bioavailability, therapeutic efficacy, and patient adherence, which could facilitate its application in targeted drug delivery systems.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

All authors participated in structuring and planning the study. Mena Safa Aziz executed material preparation, collection, and analysis of information, as well as Methaq Hamad Sabar supervised every phase of the inquiry, including the drafting of paper. All authors examined and approved the final manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Mina Safa Aziz [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-8262-0183) <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-8262-0183>

Methaq Hamad Sabar [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0909-1186) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0909-1186>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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